

Richer data, smaller models and latent representations: fair approaches in NLP

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1. Introduction

The year 2023 has seen a big leap forward in the accessibility of Generative AI with the public release of the conversational agent ChatGPT, and the sharp increase in the awareness of its capabilities and pitfalls in society at large. From being perceived as a niche discipline whose great potential was still in the distant future, the leading role natural language processing in the development of AI is now apparent to all.

After the release of ChatGPT, the potential and the danger of unbridled AI have been discussed in the news, in academia, and among policymakers resulting in the swift developing of the EU AI Act¹. A world where even just the bare bones and the basics of natural language processing is solved to a good and usable degree offers enormous possibilities. Futuristic possibilities of automation, reasoning interactive agents with fluent verbal abilities, wide-spreading machine translation that document forgotten and disappearing languages, seamless extensions to human memory in searching and summarizing appear all closely accessible. Next to the hype, the collateral fears that have always accompanied automatization arise, but the alarm has now shifted from the unlikely Hollywoodian scenario of armies of invading robots, to the much more likely situation of democracy-damaging misinformation, increased disparities, or massive undermining of academic evaluations.

Many in the NLP community are foremost sharing in the excitement while investigating the well-foundedness of these fears, with vast efforts in the evaluation of the fine-grained capabilities of Generative AI. Workshops and conferences are entirely devoted to this topic which is currently one of the most lively debated in the field (Belinkov et al., 2023). For what we can foresee now, future stumbling blocks will come from the unsustainability of the practical needs of these machines and lack

¹ <https://www.europarl.europa.eu/news/en/headlines/society/20230601STO93804/eu-ai-act-first-regulation-on-artificial-intelligence>

of trust in abilities which we do not fully understand and therefore cannot use for legal or ethical reasons.

Even before the undeniable success of large-size language models in solving many aspects of natural language processing (Tenney et al. 2019; Dale 2021), part of the scientific community had already attracted attention to the many shortcomings in their true understanding of language and does not support the idea that the trend of ever-increasing training sets is where the future of the discipline should lie (Bender et al. 2021). Large language models are problematic at various levels as, for instance, the large investment of resources that their realization requires (Strubell et al. 2019), or their tendency to reproduce and amplify the biases contained in the data on which they are trained (Swinger et al. 2019, Lu et al. 2020; Guo and Caliskan 2021).

In this paper, we draw attention to an alternative trend that embraces deep learning models in NLP, but refutes the idea that improvements in natural language processing can only be achieved by designing ever-larger size systems.

Large scale, highly integrative, comparative approaches give us a bird's eye view essential to map unknown territories, define boundaries, guide long-term trends. In NLP we see Big-bench initiatives, to better chart large language model capabilities (Srivastava et al. 2023). In neuroscience, a similar trend, dubbed integrative benchmarking, looks at large language models as mechanistic hypotheses on how the brain encodes intelligence, models that can be tested on behavioral and neural data (Schrimpf et al. 2020). Finally, another point of view has been put forth recently that, to further understand the components of human intelligence, one needs to study how this intelligence evolved, decomposing it into large-scale studies of primitive skills that humans share with other animals (Zador et al. 2023).

In this paper, we promote a closer relation between NLP and a more theoretical approach to the language sciences, in linguistics and cognitive science, by encouraging the development of algorithms whose latent representations show similarities to the ones involved in human language cognition. We also think that curated data and in-depth qualitative analyses of the intelligent behavior of these models are needed (Rogers 2021) and support the view that computational models would benefit from training, or at least testing, on smaller amounts of highly curated data, a practice well-known and widely practiced in the humanities, and that success should also comprise notions of fairness and sustainability, and cease to be measured only on benchmarked tasks.

Section 2 of the paper reviews some of the risks inherently associated with the unexamined development of large language models, as well as the factors which make their realization not sustainable. Section 3 discusses how data curation can mitigate the harmful and discriminatory potential of these technologies and presents some of the strategies deployed by the NLP community to identify biased tendencies of datasets, promote language diversity and improve observational adequacy in models. Section 4 argues for more human-like models and section 5 concludes.

2. Harm and bias in NLP

Deep learning models of extremely large size currently dominate the field of NLP (Brown et al. 2020; Fedus et al. 2021). Training a large language model requires estimating the numerical values of billions of configurational variables, or parameters, by presenting the machine with extensive datasets of unstructured data. Models of this kind are built to autonomously extract patterns and similarities from the raw data, in order to learn something about human language without any human supervision.

ChatGPT is the only publicly available large language model; it was trained using a dataset of internet-sourced data (570 gigabytes of text) and 175 billion parameters. 'GPT' stands for "Generative Pre-trained Transformer", and it refers to the way the model processes data. The accessible version of ChatGPT was launched by OpenAI in November 2022, and it is a "generative" language model which means that it can create humanlike answers to questions or compose texts.

Megatron-Turing Natural Language Generation (MT-NLG)² has an even sheerer size. It has been presented by Microsoft in 2021, but it is not publicly accessible. Training MT-NLG entailed the training of 530 billion parameters, with 15 different datasets for a total of 339 billion tokens. We notice, however, that its presentation page never mentions which languages are supported by the model, thereby indicating that while size and accuracy are considered important dimensions of evaluation, language diversity and accessibility is not.

As for ChatGPT, when questioned about the languages that it supports, it replies that it can handle a large variety of languages, although it is unable to list them all. It also clarifies its superior proficiency in English and presents it as a legitimate choice. As the ChatGPT explains "*The composition of the training dataset, including language proportions, is proprietary information and has not been disclosed publicly [...] a significant portion of the dataset is in English due to the language's global prevalence*" or, also, "a significant portion of the training data is in English, reflecting the prevalence of English content on the internet"³.

Either language diversity and accessibility are not major concerns of OpenAI or, it is simply impossible to care for these issues with language models of this size, since the problem of retrieving enough training data can hardly be obviated even for English, as illustrated by the 2023 legal action carried out by the New York Times against both Microsoft and OpenAI⁴.

The success achieved by large-size language models in performing specific tasks has revived the belief that increased size is the best predictor for the success of a model (Brown et al. 2020). The resources and efforts put in the development of ever larger systems has allowed state-of-the-art models to grow from ELMo's 94 million parameters in 2018 to MT-NLG, in just 5 years.

Moreover, the unprecedented task-oriented success that large-size models currently display has brought about the idea that a model's linguistic competence resembles or even surpasses what humans can do. In fact, language models are designed to manipulate certain aspects of natural languages which are dependent on their parameters, and can only do that within the limits of the data that they are trained on. The semantics derived automatically from language corpora are not human-like in all respects, as they are more superficial, are not grounded in the real world, and can contain illogical associations that humans would never consider. For instance, in December 2017, the American filmmaker Dan Mirvish observed a consistent correlation between the actress Anne Hathaway making headlines and a surge in Berkshire-Hathaway Inc.'s stocks⁵. The phenomenon was imputed to the way computerized trading models, which are NLP models, look for correlations in the internet chatters, and to their finding the Hathaway correlation that has no correspondence in the real world⁶.

² <https://www.microsoft.com/en-us/research/blog/using-deepspeed-and-megatron-to-train-megatron-turing-nlg-530b-the-worlds-largest-and-most-powerful-generative-language-model/>

³ ChatGPT answering questions like: "In what percentage the data used for your training was in English?"

⁴ <https://www.nytimes.com/2023/12/27/business/media/new-york-times-open-ai-microsoft-lawsuit.html>

⁵ https://www.huffpost.com/entry/the-hathaway-effect-how-a_b_830041

⁶ <https://www.theatlantic.com/technology/archive/2011/03/does-anne-hathaway-news-drive-berkshire-hathaways-stock/72661/>

Problems of this kind place current large language models at the center of controversy: their functioning depends on complex architectures and relies on training over enormous quantities of raw data. Because data curation can only be effectively conducted on a small scale, large language models inevitably develop an image of the external world which is shaped by the data they can access. This becomes a problem when the worldview generated by the model inherits the discriminatory tendencies present in the data, a fact that leads the scientific community to question whether big models can ever be deployed without harm (Bender et al. 2021).

2.1. Fairness

The internet is a global network of networks; however, despite its being publicly accessible, there are factors such as gender, age or income level, that narrow down people's participation. This means that a large dataset of raw data gathered from a given internet source will not be representative of the global population, but will reflect the language and, with that, the view of the world predominant class of users of any given service. The issue with fairness arises when the narrowness of the data sources is not acknowledged.

Wikipedia articles represent a good example of a demographically imbalanced dataset. Wikipedia is a large, publicly accessible, multilingual encyclopaedia maintained by volunteer authors. According to the data released by the organisation in 2011, 72% of the authors are younger than 40 years old, about 80% are male and, within the first ten countries where most of the authors reside only one, India, is not in Europe or North America⁷. More recent studies show that its digital inequalities are persistent (Shawn and Hargittai 2018; Steinkasserer et al. 2020).

While one can identify Wikipedia's demographic gaps, no demographic information is available for most other internet sources of linguistic data. And yet, there is no reason to think that the same disparities do not occur. According to the World Bank, only 14% of people living in low-revenue countries have regular internet access, compared to 89% of people living in high-revenue ones⁸. The Web's attested deficit of geographic diversity inevitably entails lack of fairness in data harvested from it. Raw data of this sort, in fact, are not representative of different ways to see the world, but mostly represent restricted groups of people with similar demographic profiles, interests and, most probably, the same biases.

Bias manifests itself in discriminatory behaviours of which individuals have no awareness; language conveys human biases and, consequently, NLP models derived automatically from large corpora of raw data display such discriminatory tendencies too. This is how misogynistic, racist, ageistic etc. attitudes permeate technology and cause harm to a discriminated group (Ma et al. 2023). For example, word embeddings, which are semantic representations of word relations, have been shown to collect the same discriminatory associations found in the raw data they are trained on (Swinger et al. 2019). They are largely used to implement sentiment analysis tasks, and their real-life applications provide excellent examples of harmful bias.

Sentiment classification is obtained by teaching a classifier to evaluate a positive/negative score of some text by calculating how close the words in the text are to lists of gold-standard good and bad words. As Speer showed already in 2017, a sentiment analysis of restaurant reviews implemented on neural networks systematically assigns lower scores to Mexican restaurants than it does to other

⁷ <https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Wikipedia:Wikipedians#Demographics> and *Wikipedia editors study: results from the editor survey*. https://meta.wikimedia.org/wiki/Research:Wikipedia_Editors_Survey_2011_April

⁸ <https://data.worldbank.org/indicator/IT.NET.USER.ZS>

groups of restaurants⁹. This happens because word embeddings learn the meaning of words from the Web, and in the Web the term “Mexican” is frequently associated with heavily negative words such as “illegal”, resulting in the attribution of a negative sentiment score to any Mexican restaurant review.

Large scale models are exceedingly good at picking up correlations and, due to their architecture, they cannot be prevented from identifying unwanted and offensive correlations present in the large bulk of data required for their training.

2.2. Sustainability

Demographic groups whose voice is scarcely represented on the internet constitute the complementary side of the problem; they are virtually invisible to large-size NLP models because they produce a very limited amount of linguistic resources. This way the lack of demographic representativeness also becomes a lack of linguistic diversity and representativeness in NLP and language technology in general.

As mentioned earlier, the collection of large amounts of copyright free data for English is nearly impossible (Karamolegkou et al. 2023), but for about half of the more than 7000 living languages of the world there is no written data at all. These are languages for which there is no written codification (Eberhard et al. 2021), and they are therefore excluded from any NLP model that relies on written linguistic input. The absence of a writing system, however, is not the sole obstacle that language diversity faces in NLP: according to “Whose knowledge?” report¹⁰ (2018), the internet only captures approximately 500 different languages, indicating that there is very little raw data for most other tongues. This state of affairs is due to the lower internet participation rate in countries where material resources are scarce, to the fact that most language diversity originates in these regions and, also, to the absence of technologies able to support the specificities of such linguistic codes.

This is not yet the last barrier that linguistic diversity must face in NLP: even among the languages that are indeed represented on the internet, major differences in terms of available data can be observed. According to E. Bender's estimation, large quantities of digital data are only available for a handful of languages, mainly English, Mandarin Chinese, Arabic and French¹¹. To a lesser degree, abundant resources also exist for German, Portuguese, Spanish and Finnish. The ones in the list can be classified as “high-resource” languages, whereas the remaining living languages of the world are “low-resource” ones.

The skewed distribution of digital linguistic resources poses a major sustainability issue for large scale models. Their implementation faces unsolvable problems of documentation debt for the 99.9% of natural languages, at least according to the basic rationale that large unsupervised NLP models rely for their functioning on large quantities of raw data, and large quantity of raw data are only available for the 0.1% of the world languages.

Sustainability of large language models is also problematic when it comes down to their opportunity costs. In a world of finite resources, the amount of human and material resources invested in the development of models of this type results in a sizable cutback in what can be allotted for the development of more inclusive technologies. In addition to this, sustainability is further aggravated by claims of language independence in models which are only tested on a limited set of typologically

⁹ <http://blog.conceptnet.io/posts/2017/how-to-make-a-racist-ai-without-really-trying/>

¹⁰ Whose Knowledge? 2020. *Decolonizing the Internet's Languages*.

<https://whoseknowledge.org/resource/dtil-report/?lang=fr>

¹¹ <https://thegradient.pub/the-benderrule-on-naming-the-languages-we-study-and-why-it-matters/>

similar languages (Bender 2011). While their language-agnostic properties remain unsubstantiated for most languages, they attract investments which deepen the divide between high and low-resource languages in NLP.

2.2. Dual use

The last issue we will mention here concerns the languages for which there is indeed enough data to train large language models with flawless generating abilities like, for example, ChatGPT. Their human-like output raises the issue of "dual use". Dual use is intended as the intentional harmful resume of technologies and artefacts. While dual use of AI has been discussed before (Shankar and Zare, 2022; Ratner, 2021; Gamage et al., 2021), NLP is a new arrival and true understanding of potential dual use of Large Language Models is only now developing (Kaffee et al. 2023).

The dual use prevention regulations of the European Union¹² as well as the code of ethics of the Association for Computing Machinery¹³ require NLP professionals to put in place procedures to identify foreseeable misuses of their artefact. Measures to mitigate eventual harmful effects should be implemented but NLP professionals are not necessarily equipped to identify or block malicious intents. The literature reports alarming ethical and practical challenges emerging from the use of large language models in the medical field. For instance, Biron reported on *The Business Insider* in 2023¹⁴, the case of an online mental health service which relied on ChatGPT to advise people asking for help. Although, the potential harm of letting a machine give advice to people in a fragile condition is obvious, misuses of this kind can hardly be averted upstream even if mitigation techniques are deployed. In addition to this, harm-mitigating techniques are not always effective. ChatGPT safety mechanisms are designed to avert the model from providing unethical replies, but Spennemann (2023) proves that little effort is needed to generate prompts which are able to bypass the filter and trick the system into providing clever suggestions to cheat in academic assignments. The wide-ranging social impact of these models indicates that NLP professionals cannot be left alone in ensuring their responsible usage.

3. Curated data as probe

Implicit bias is an undesirable and unavoidable byproduct of the way humans organise their knowledge of the physical world. As Rosh explains, our reality is not perceived as an unstructured set of attributes, but rather the objects of the world are understood to occur in a correlational structure which makes us see the co-occurrence of certain attributes as more frequent than other combinations of properties (Rosh 1998). For instance, attributes such as "wings" and "feathers" form a more stable association than "fur" and "wings" do.

Not every association of attributes is immutable, since there are many factors that influence our ability to perceive reality; some of them are species-specific, our senses, whereas others result from our interaction as individuals with our social environment and its culture at a given time. For example, the attributes associated with the terms like "woman", "Indian" or "homosexual" change across cultures

¹² See f.n. 1.

¹³ ACM Code of Ethics and Professional Conduct. 2018.

<https://www.acm.org/binaries/content/assets/membership/images2/fac-stu-poster-code.pdf>

¹⁴ Bethany Biron. 2023. Online mental health company uses ChatGPT to help respond to users in experiment—raising ethical concerns around healthcare and AI technology. *Business Insider*.

<https://www.businessinsider.com/company-using-chatgpt-mental-health-support-ethical-issues-2023-1?r=US&IR=T>

and change over time. Implicit biases come from associations of this type, and they are discriminatory whenever they lead to problematic harmful behaviours.

Since biases originate from innate cognitive systems, human behaviour is often biased and so is language. This means that the introduction of biases in a dataset made of raw linguistic data is unavoidable and it is a major problem in a world where machine learning increasingly affects society. However, just like awareness is a mitigating factor for human biases because it makes individuals be accountable for their harmful behaviour, the awareness of how bias infiltrates a model at different levels is the most effective way to mitigate its harmful tendencies and move towards fairer and more sustainable practices.

3.1 Bias control in datasets

Human biased perceptions are shaped by many different factors. In the same way, there are multifarious inlets for bias to cause downstream harm via an NLP model. Bias can be "historical", when a model represents the discriminatory tendencies of the actual world, whereas "representational" biases coincide with the knowledge gaps present in the input data and arise from a sampling mistake; biases can also arise from a "measurement" error, whereby the wrong data is selected to measure a phenomenon, like using arrest-rate as proxy for crime-rate (Suresh and Guttag 2019).

While there is not a cure-all for bias in NLP, the issues caused by it can be alleviated by gaining an improved awareness of the possible discriminatory tendency that a model could inherit in its training phase. This can be achieved by investing time and financial resources in data curation, by adopting standardised curation practices, and by making careful data curation be a compulsory or compensatory step in the development of natural language processing tools.

For example, data sampling by careful criteria developed over the years by linguists and corpus linguistics researchers could be revived. It used to be the case that stylistics and linguistics factors had to be carefully controlled to be able to call a data collection a 'corpus'. In principle, any collection of more than one text can be called a corpus. But the term *corpus* used to have, and still has in certain scientific communities, more specific connotations. Corpora in these domains are collections of text that are fixed beforehand, to ensure that some of the construction criteria, like balancing, can be applied. In particular, it is implied that the corpus is representative. In order for a collection of text to indeed be representative, it has to be sampled in accurate ways. The most often used method is stratified sampling, i.e. the creation of a balanced collection of texts that are evenly distributed across the genres and modalities of interest. For example, the Brown Corpus is a standard reference of present day, written American English (Francis and Kucera, 1987), the British National Corpus of British English (BNC)¹⁵ and so on.

From a statistical point of view a corpus is a sample of a population of linguistic events. Like other samples, it is subject to two possible kinds of errors: random error and bias error. Random errors occur when the sample is too small to have confidence in the sample's representativeness of the true population. For example, a single interview of a teenager would not be a good example of the use of language of all teenagers. In general terms, bias error occurs when a sample's characteristics are systematically different from those of the population it should represent. For example, if one were to use only the financial section of the New York Times, no matter how big the sample, this would not be a representative corpus of nowadays American English, nor is the speech of teenagers representative of the language use of all ages (McEnery and Hardie, 2011). In the same way, a collection of texts

¹⁵ BNC Consortium, *The British National Corpus, XML Edition*, 2007, Oxford Text Archive, <http://hdl.handle.net/20.500.12024/2554>.

gathered from social media, will only be a corpus representative of the language utilised by the dominant class of users of that service and will systematically contain the biased associations that prevail within that restricted community.

Several annotated corpora are being used these days both for NLP, the technological side of computational linguistics, and also for computational linguistics proper. Annotation is another way of curating data that can reduce biases. The act of annotating a treebank is an act of research in large-coverage grammar (Marcus et al. 1993; Abeille, 2003; De Marneffe et al., 2021) and annotating a corpus semantically requires developing large coverage semantic theories (Palmer et al., 2005). Moreover, multilingual annotation schemes require knowledge in typology (De Marneffe et al., 2021). All of the above suggest that linguistic theory should be considered a tool to improve annotation tasks and overall data curation.

Carefully sampling, carefully detailed linguistics annotation of large samples of typologically diverse languages are several ways of combating the wide-spread mistaken opinion that at web-scale quantity becomes quality, well exemplified by Halevy, Norvig and Pereira (2009). We are aware now that this point of view is no longer tenable without qualification.

Thorough data curation is expensive and time consuming; for this reason, it has been proposed that all NLP projects should systematically include it as an item of their budget (Bender et al. 2021). The good practice entailed by this principle is that models must be designed to train on as much data as can be thoroughly documented within that budget.

Proposals on standardised data documentation practises have been put forward in recent years (Bender and Friedman 2018; Gebru et al. 2021). The rationale behind such proposals is to provide an accurate characterization of the datasets in order to contextualise the experimental results, and to estimate in advance whether an application can be deployed without harm. Datasheets of the proposed kind must record information not only about the data, but also about the demographic profile of the dataset curators, the founding agency and any other possible agent who can potentially introduce bias in the system pipeline.

Finally, self-regulation of the field is a propulsive factor to increase the community's concerns with ethical considerations. For this reason, starting with 2021, ACL encourages authors of scientific papers not only to submit rich documentation about the data used in their research but, also, their own reflections on the potential harm which a system can cause once it is deployed¹⁶.

3.2 Cure for language diversity

Low-resourcedness is an issue reflecting systemic problems of society which NLP cannot directly solve; large datasets of raw written digital data cannot be created for languages whose population of speakers have limited access to technology, nor for languages for which a writing system or the hardware support like an appropriate keyboard has never been developed. Nevertheless, the scarcity of linguistic resources that affects most natural languages should not be seen as an insurmountable obstacle to transform NLP into a universal discipline. This though this goal requires a major turnaround in the way models are conceived which is the core topic of the Widening NLP (WinLP¹⁷) conference reaching its seventh edition in 2023 (Bonaventure et al. 2023).

Sustainable NLP must focus on the development of language models which are less reliant on large quantities of data. One of such creative alternatives consists in the inclusion of participants with no

¹⁶ <https://aclrollingreview.org/authorchecklist> section: "Responsible NLP research".

¹⁷ <https://www.winlp.org/>

specific NLP training in a model's development process (Nekoto et al. 2020). In the case at hand this means the adoption of a participatory approach for the creation of datasets and benchmarks for low resources African languages and, also, its adoption in the model evaluation phase. Participatory evaluation is particularly important to test the ability of a multilingual model to deal with resource language. Their performance, in fact, is hardly assessable with more traditional tools as crowdsourcing platforms, since speakers of low-resource languages are underrepresented in the communities targeted by these methods.

Sustainable NLP therefore requires to reframe the success obtained by large scale multilingual models with respect to their real ability to handle language diversity. Part of the NLP community has exposed the notion that multilanguage models operating with no human supervision can indeed be language-agnostic, precisely because they are trained on English and a few other languages (Bender 2011). Nonetheless, this belief somehow persists; high-resource languages benefit from constant academic interest and technological advancement¹⁸, and many NLP practitioners continue to operate under the assumption that the treatment of low-resource ones can be implemented by transferring the same technology from one group to the other, contrary to what has been observed (Joshi et al. 2020).

Consequently, the first step to cure language diversity in NLP is to "always name the language that you are working on" (a.k.a, the *Bender Rule*¹⁹). Naming the languages dealt by a piece of research in a transparent fashion creates awareness on the potential limitations of a given model. It is apparently a trivial practice, but is not an established one, as illustrated by the absence of language specification in the presentation of some large models like, for example, MT-NLG²⁰.

3.3. Adequacy

One last aspect of data curation which deserves discussion is its contribution to the development of observationally adequate linguistic models. Observational adequacy is a level of empirical adequacy that any formal linguistic analysis must meet (Chomsky 1964); it allows to correctly predict the forms that exist in a language and the ones that do not.

Given that linguistic data follow the Zipfian distribution, models designed to train on large datasets of raw data struggle to learn any generalisation related to rare linguistic phenomena. Zipf's law demonstrates that most linguistic phenomena occur at a low frequency in natural language samples, which means that any dataset of raw data will rarely provide sufficiently rich input for a model to autonomously learn such features (Zipf 1945, Rogers, 2021).

For example, it has been shown that a model can learn to deal with rare syntactic phenomena like *wh*-dependencies by pretraining it with a dataset of 10M token, as long as the sample reliably encodes the set of tested syntactic features (Zhang et al. 2020). As the authors of the study explain, this is a remarkable improvement in scalability, considering that the same level of accuracy without targeted pre-training requires billions of training tokens.

Thus, the use of curated training data allows the developer to control for a model's exposure to every observable linguistic phenomenon, unlike what happens with raw datasets. However, the use of pretraining datasets of this type is still not sufficient for a model to master natural language understanding tasks, whose implementation appears to require additional pretraining with billions of words (Zhang et al. 2020).

¹⁸ <http://www.marekrei.com/blog/geographic-diversity-of-nlp-conferences/>

¹⁹ See f.n. 11.

²⁰ See f.n. 2.

While the dominant method to train machine learning models is to use observational data found in large web-scale corpora, it is not the only one. Another way to develop machine learning models that is more easily controlled for bias is to use counterfactual experimental techniques, like in the experimental sciences. One way to discover which counterbalancing biases can be injected in large language models, is to study humans. Humans' understanding of language relies on far smaller quantities of data, and the investigations of the similarities between the models and us are discussed in the following section.

4. Machines that function like humans

One of the most intuitive ways of developing more human-like machines for many languages is to take inspiration from humans themselves. Large efforts are underway in the community of natural language processing, cognitive science and computational models in linguistics to investigate the inner workings of current neural network architectures. Part of this research is driven by the wish to understand to what extent the functioning of language models can be compared to that of humans. We give here three examples, derived from work on the lexicon and on syntax, which study questions that are crucially related to the association biases we have discussed above, namely: what notion of similarity is represented in these distributed spaces, and what phenomena or representations it captures. We also test current conversational AI agents to sound their analytic capabilities.

The lexicon exhibits a rich structure, encoding various semantic relations among words, tied by derivations and compositional processes. In addition to word contextual associations, people are sensitive to components of the meaning of words, and their relation to each other in highly connected classification structures. We can consider the class of “motion verbs” to illustrate this point. The internal semantic structure of the verbs allows the elements belonging to the class of motion verbs to be further classified according to how they are composed: verbs composed of a specification of movement and manner of movement are referred as “manner of motion” verbs (e.g. *run*, *stride*), whereas verbs composed of a specification of movement plus a directional component are referred as “directed motion” verbs (e.g. *leave*, *arrive*). Words are thus linked to each other by complex networks of semantic similarity but also by productive derivational processes that determine both the families of semantic association they belong to and their syntactic and morphological neighbourhoods (Levin 1993, McCarthy and Korhonen 1998, Merlo and Stevenson 2001, Schulte and Walde 2006).

The distributional approach to word meaning successfully captures word contextual associations, producing representations that perform well on semantic tasks such as similarity and analogy (Schuetze 1994; Collobert and Weston 2007; Mikolov et al. 2013). More recent methods have integrated more complex architectures, such as transformers, achieving contextualised and adaptable models (Devlin et al., 2019). It is these dynamic models that underpin current large language models, and that exhibit much of the associative biases we have discussed above.

Comparisons to human association spaces, monolingually and bilingually, of these dynamic models, show that they are good mirrors of the human mental lexicon. So: What do people know when they know the meaning of words? Word associations have been widely used to tap into lexical representations and their structure, as a way of probing semantic knowledge in humans. Rodriguez and Merlo (2020) show that current context-aware word embedding spaces have comparable characteristics to human association spaces, in particular they present three crucial properties which show that word association spaces are not simply multidimensional geometric spaces, but they have unusual properties of asymmetry of similarity and violations of triangle inequality. Not only are monolingual word embeddings good models of associations, but multilingual word embeddings have

also shown to be good models of human bilingual lexicon. Merlo and Rodriguez (2019) show that multilingual spaces exhibit transfer effects -- where the source language influences the semantic space of the target language -- that are consistent with the cross-language influences seen in human bilinguals (van Hell and Degroot 1998, Degani et al. 2011).

By understanding more clearly how words are associated in distributed spaces and how a source language can influence a target language, better means might be determined for anticipating bias in distributed representations or in transfer learning towards low-resource languages and alleviating it.

Another core distinguishing property of human language is the ability to interpret discontinuous elements as if they were a single element. These are called long-distance dependencies. For example, in an object relative clause, such as *Paul knows the speaker that the student admires unreservedly*, the object of the verb *admires* is also the semantic object of the verb *knows* connecting two distant elements. Previously established results showed that neural networks can detect number agreement at a distance and can learn agreement patterns in four languages with almost human performance (Linzen et al 2016; Gulordava et al. 2018). We also know that neural networks can detect filler-gap dependencies, like the relative clause shown above (Wilcox et al. 2018; Merlo and Ackermann 2018, Merlo 2019, Samo and Merlo 2023).

Building representations for these constructions requires not only word associations, but ability to build structure and to manage a memory that keeps track of long-distance associations. Thus, we can look at long-distance operations that produce acceptable grammatical sentences, as a way to look into memory mechanisms that might develop associations over time and across long segments of text and influence and bias text interpretations in very indirect ways.

Finally, how do we evaluate LLMs, determine the aspects and limits of their intelligent behaviour and compare them to human intelligence?

One fundamental observation is that humans are good generalizers. One likely reason why people generalise better is that they have a strong prior bias, grounded in the actual structure of the problem. To reach human-like abilities machines must show that they can achieve good generalisation, be it across languages, across domains, or new unseen combinatorial tokens and structures (Hupkes et al. 2022).

To this end, and similar to the IQ test called RPM (Raven's Progressive Matrices) for vision, a new linguistic task has been developed called Blackbird Language Matrices (BLMs) (Merlo 2023a). RPMs are IQ tests consisting of a matrix of images connected in a logical sequence by underlying generative rules (Raven 1938). The task is to determine a missing element. The answer is chosen among a set of closely or loosely similar alternatives. BLMs apply the same logic. They define a prediction task based on complex linguistic patterns and paradigms. Because this task relies on a mixture of language and abstract rule learning abilities, we conjecture that BLMs can be appropriately used in evaluation settings to investigate not only the limits and properties of linguistic intelligence in large language models, but also how they compare to humans' language ability.

The task has been administered to ChatGPT 4 (Merlo 2023b). If we map impressionistically ChatGPT's solutions to the three areas in which people find difficulty in solving IQ RPM tests, correspondence finding, handling item novelty and management of rules and sub-rules, we find that ChatGPT is quite good at correspondence finding --the identification of the relevant objects and their attributes--, but only if the problem encodes a single grammatical rule. Also, it clearly performs better with lexical semantic problems than morphological problems. Concerning item novelty, if explicit instructions are provided, the model seems to be able to identify an abstract template from lexically varied items. However, it never manages to identify the sequence pattern, and consequently find the answer in any of the problems which seems to be indicative of lack of goal and sub-goal management.

This test further corroborates the main point of view of this chapter. The investigation reported here aims to prove a concept: curated data and in-depth qualitative analyses inspired by human intelligence tests can complement large-scale benchmarking in an interesting way. In particular, large-scale benchmarking based on correlations of humans and machines does not enlighten us on the causal sources of behaviours, and instead hypothesis testing experiments need to be performed.

5. Conclusions

In this paper, we have argued that natural language processing should tend towards models trained with highly curated datasets to increase language diversity and should take inspiration from human abilities to better understand the working of the large models in use today.

Current training methods based on prediction of the next word (Devlin et al. 2019 among many), and resulting models are not powerful enough to always identify underlying rules and representations as humans naturally do. To develop more human-like, linguistically aware and adaptable systems, we need to develop new data sets and tasks, anchored in decades on linguistics and psycholinguistics research, on which we train and validate current machine learning models that learn to categorise, generalise and abstract, and that in so doing can handle a variety of languages, even those with limited resources.

This approach, inspired by the long tradition of carefully curated data and sources in the humanities, puts us in control of the data and can counterbalance the harmful effects observed in language models which require large amounts of raw data to be trained. Ever-larger language models are not the sole research direction of NLP: models designed to function with smaller amounts of highly curated data represent a valid alternative and could help us understand more about the functioning of human language cognition.

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